

COPING MECHANISMS TO ENHANCE SELF-CONFIDENCE AND SKILLS IN PUBLIC SPEAKING AMONG GRADE 12 STUDENTS AT MINDANAO STATE UNIVERSITY-SULU

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the study was to investigate the coping mechanisms to enhance self-confidence and skills in public speaking among grade 12 students at Mindanao State University–Sulu. The adapted survey questionnaire was utilized in this study. 280 respondents of grade 12 GAS and STEM students currently enrolled in Mindanao State University-Sulu selected through stratified random sampling. A rating scale and Likert scale survey questionnaire was used to gather the data. The findings revealed that the respondents generally applied the coping mechanisms to improve public speaking skills presented by the researchers. Thus, the researchers concluded that there is a relationship between coping mechanisms and self-confidence and skills in public speaking. Therefore, the researchers recommended that students could enhance their self-confidence and skills in public speaking by practicing, using healthy coping strategies, establishing peer support groups, and utilizing technology and multimedia tools. These strategies can help lessen fear, provide a secure environment for practice, and foster a sense of comfort with public speaking: Future researchers should conduct further studies based on the coping mechanisms to enhance self-confidence and skills in public speaking in different settings: Teachers should use creative techniques to evaluate students' academic performance and encourage self-confidence and public speaking skills, while fostering a secure and motivating classroom environment: Parents should teach their children to communicate with everyone. They should boost their children's confidence level in public speaking. Proper guidance from parents will help the students

to enhance their self-confidence and skills in public speaking. Simple linear regression analysis.

Keywords: *Coping Mechanisms, Self-Confidence, Public Speaking Skills.*

INTRODUCTION

Self-confidence in public speaking refers to belief in one's ability to effectively communicate and express thoughts, ideas, or messages to an audience (Zhang et al., 2020). This confidence enables a speaker to convey their message clearly, maintain composure, and engage the audience. The ability of students to successfully express ideas, participate actively in class debate and thrive in a variety of career pathways is greatly influenced by their level of confidence in public speaking (Permatasiri, 2024).

Self-confidence in public speaking is important to master because not all students have the skills to speak in public or society (Dansieh et. al., 2021). Currently, especially student has a desire to be normal in everyday life, like other students. The ability to communicate is an important need for students to be able to express their heart and minds so that it is easier to complete their activities and assignments by participating in conversation with others. But not all students are confidence enough to stand in front of the class, or to present, the reason for the look of practice, poor mastery of the students or feeling afraid when they speak in public.

Based on the analysis, state anxiety appeared to be the main problem for the students (Dias Lopes, 2020). Shy pupils avoid speaking, offer brief responses to queries in the target language, and prefer to remain alone. They have modest communication challenges, are sluggish to express their emotions. Self-confidence has an influence on pupils' speaking abilities. In other words, students with high self-confidence are more likely to speak English better those of with low self-confidence. Improving student confidence in public speaking can enhance their speaking abilities and can help them to get better, especially when speaking to an audience or society. This research aims to investigate the students' self-confidence in public speaking among grade 12 students at Mindanao State University-Sulu.

The Philippines like many other nations, faces challenge in education particularly in the realm of public speaking. This can create places where students lack confidence in their public speaking abilities leading to decreased participation in classroom discussion, presentations, and other public speaking activities, potentially impacting their overall public speaking confidence. Speaking in front of a lot of people takes a lot of courage and confidence to properly explain and deliver what you are really trying to emphasize to the audience. Inayah and Lisdawati (2021) highlighted that students who are having difficulties speaking in front of a lot of people are often lacking in self-confidence as a result, it hinders their ability to express themselves convincingly in front of a crowd. Students who lack confidence will also lack the courage to speak up in front of other students because they lack the courage to engage in public conversation or typically hesitate to act (Ananda & Hastini 2023).

The main objective of this study is to investigate the effectiveness of coping mechanisms in enhancing self-confidence and improving public speaking skills among Grade 12 students at Mindanao State University-Sulu. Recognizing the challenges many students face when speaking publicly, such as anxiety, fear, and low self-esteem. This research seeks to assess how specific strategies like preparation, positive thinking, and peer support contribute to students' ability to communicate effectively in front of an audience. By exploring the relationship between these coping mechanisms and students' self-confidence, the study aims to provide evidence-based recommendations for educational practices that can foster a supportive environment for developing strong public speaking competencies.

Research Questions

This study aims to assess the application of coping mechanisms to enhance self-confidence in public speaking. Specifically, the study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. To what extent do grade 12 students at Mindanao State University-Sulu senior high school apply the coping mechanisms to improve public speaking skills?
2. What is the level of self-confidence in public speaking of the students?
3. Is the application of coping mechanisms enhancing their level of self-confidence in public speaking?

METHODOLOGY

Research design

The researcher employed a quantitative descriptive research design to describe and analyze the relationship between coping mechanisms and self-confidence in public speaking among Grade 12 students at Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School (SHS). Descriptive research design systematically describes or analyzes a phenomenon or population's characteristics or relationships without manipulating variables, focusing on answering "what," "how," or "why" questions.

Research Site

This study was conducted at Mindanao State University Sulu senior high school Department during the school year 2024 - 2025. The only university in Sulu is located at Capitol Site Patikul Sulu, near the Sulu Provincial Capital. The said department consists of two buildings exclusively for classrooms and head office.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were 280 senior high school students as determined using Raosoft Online Sample Size Calculator from Mindanao State University Sulu. This was selected through stratified random sampling to ensure representation across GAS and STEM strand. The table below illustrates the number of respondents in each and every section.

Table 1. Representation of the sample Size in every Section

Sections	Population	Sample
STEM 1-12	79	22
STEM 2-12	81	22
STEM 3-12	78	22
STEM 4-12	76	21
STEM 5-12	83	23
STEM 6-12	82	22
GAS 1-12	74	20
GAS 2-12	75	20
GAS 3-12	75	20
GAS 4-12	75	21
GAS 5-12	80	22
GAS 6-12	83	23
GAS 7-12	81	22
TOTAL	1022	280

Research Instrument

The researchers used the adapted survey questionnaire for the data gathering process to get quantitative information. The questionnaire was structured in such a way that respondents will be able to answer it easily. The following are the references for the questionnaires used by the researchers; Sawchuk (2024), Shelton-Strong and Mynard (2018), Yaikhong and Usaha (2012),

The researchers are already done with the CVI and part 1: Coping mechanisms to improve public speaking skills. The result of S-CVI/Ave is 0.93, total agreement is 12, and S-CVI/UA is 2.76. Part 2: Self-confidence in public speaking. The S-CVI/Ave is 0.93, total agreement is 8, and S-CVI/UA is 1.84. The Cronbach's alpha of the reliability test is .870.

The questionnaire was made of two parts: the first part was coping mechanisms to enhance public speaking skills which compose of 15 statements and measures through rating scale for frequency (Often, Always, Sometimes, Rarely, Never), while the second part was the self-confidence in public speaking which compose of 10 statements and measures through Likert scale (Strongly Agree, Agree, Neither Agree or Disagree, Disagree, Strongly Disagree).

Data Collection

Data Collection was planned over a three-week period with survey questionnaires distributed during scheduled class sessions. To collect the data, the researchers sent a letter of approval to the director of senior high school department to ask permission to conduct a survey. After the letter was approved, the researchers administered the survey questionnaire and tabulated the data.

Statistical technique

The data was analyzed using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences), a comprehensive and widely recognized software tool for advanced statistical analysis. Specifically, Median is used to answer the extent of grade 12 students at Mindanao State University-Sulu senior high school apply the coping mechanisms to improve public speaking skills and level of self-confidence in public speaking of the students. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to explore the relationship between the extent of application of coping mechanisms and self-confidence in public speaking.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2. Coping Mechanisms to Improve Public Speaking Skills

Indicators	Md	Description
1. Know the topic.	4.00	Always
2. Think positive.	4.00	Always
3. Practice makes perfect.	4.00	Always

4. Slow down and take deep breaths.	4.00	Always
5. Think before you speak.	4.00	Always
6. Get organized.	3.50	Always
7. Know the audience.	3.00	Sometimes
8. Focus on the material, not audience.	3.00	Sometimes
9. Use non-verbal communication.	3.00	Sometimes
10. Use notes during speech.	3.00	Sometimes
11. Tell stories.	3.00	Sometimes

Note: 1.00= Never; 2,00= Rarely; 3.00= Sometimes; 4.00= Always; 5.00= Often.

Table 2 shows the level of frequency on how students applied coping mechanisms to improve public speaking skills among grade 12 students at Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School. The responses are measured using a median (Md) score. The respondents **always** applied coping mechanisms such as *knowing the topic, thinking positively, practicing making perfect, slow down and take deep breaths, think before you speak, and get organized* as illustrated in the table with a median score of 4.00. Respondents **sometimes** used the following coping mechanism; *know the audience, focus on the material, not audience, use non-verbal communication, use notes during speech, and tell stories* which have median score of 3.00. These suggest that students have generally applied the coping mechanisms to improve public speaking skills presented by the researchers.

Numerous methods have been demonstrated to improve pupils' English-speaking and public speaking abilities. Pratiwi et.al., (2024) claimed that while conversational practice promotes gains in English pronunciation and vocabulary, the manuscript technique helps learners become more self-assured and improves their pronunciation, speaking patterns, and vocabulary. The question-and-answer method successfully improves speaking skills among 12th grade students at Mindanao State University-Sulu (Putri et. al., 2024). In a similar vein, Safitri et.al. (2023) emphasized that by raising students' interest, self-assurance, and excitement for learning, storytelling can greatly enhance public speaking abilities.

Table 3. Level of Self-Confidence in Public Speaking of the Students

Indicators	Md	Description
1. I have ability to speak English.	4.00	Agree
2. If I do my best to achieve my learning goals.	4.00	Agree
3. I believe in myself.	4.00	Agree
4. I feel confident in myself.	4.00	Agree
5. I trust my feelings and emotions.	4.00	Agree
6. I enjoy experience of speaking English.	4.00	Agree
7. I usually speak English during class participation.	3.00	Neither Agree nor Disagree

8. I have no fear of speaking English.	3.00	Neither Agree nor Disagree
9. I face the prospect English with confidence.	3.00	Neither Agree nor Disagree
Grand Median	4.00	Agree

Note: 1.00= Strongly Disagree; 2.00= Disagree; 3.00= Neither Agree nor Disagree; 4.00= Agree; 5.00= Strongly Agree.

Table 3 shows the level of self-confidence in public speaking of the students. As presented in table, respondents **agreed** to the following statements: *having the ability to speak English, do the best to achieve learning goals, believe in self, feel confident in self, trust in feelings and emotions, and enjoy experience of speaking English* where median scores are 4.00. Otherwise, respondents have lack of agreements on the statements that follow; *to speak English during class participation, have no fear of speaking English, and face the prospect English with confidence* were median scores are 3.0. The overall grand median score of 4.00 which means Agree suggests that students are confident enough to speak English publicly.

Statements 7 to 9 received a median score of 3.00, indicating neutral responses. According to Achekzai (2024), encouraging students to speak English during class participation can be achieved by fostering their self-confidence, providing engaging assignments, cultivating supportive relationships, and creating a positive learning environment. Although speaking English in class causes little fear for most students, some individuals may still experience nervousness when speaking in front of large groups (Kella, 2021). To help learners face the prospect of speaking English with confidence, it is important to address the challenges related to speech production. As Axrorovna and Baxtiyorovna (2020) explain, this essay focuses on enhancing students' confidence in speaking English by examining the difficulties commonly encountered by English language learners.

Diverse viewpoints on the connection between speaking performance and self-confidence are presented by research. Higher self-confidence is often associated with stronger public speaking abilities, according to certain studies (Aqso et al., 2023; Salsabila et al., 2023), but other studies present a more nuanced picture. With an average score of 4.0, Nadiah (2019) found that students' self-confidence in public speaking was generally moderate. These results suggest that although speaking ability can be influenced by self-confidence, performance is not solely determined by it.

Table 4. Regression analysis on Coping Mechanisms to enhance Self-Confidence in Public Speaking

Model	Unstandardized B coefficients	Standardized β Coefficients	R	R Square	p-value
(Constant)	1.735				< .001
Coping mechanisms to	.529	.420	.420	.177	< .001

A simple linear regression was used to determine the impact of coping mechanism to enhance self-confidence in public speaking. The result revealed that for every unit 1 increases coping mechanisms to enhance public speaking, it leads to .529 increase self confidence in public speaking. Hence, coping mechanisms to enhance public speaking ($\beta = .420$, $p < .001$) is positive impact self-confidence. The regression coefficients are positive, indicating that if coping mechanisms apply, self-confidence increases. The R-square (.177) signifies that about 17.7% of self-confidence can be explained by coping mechanisms. 82.3% can be explained by other variables.

Various tactics, like practicing pronunciation, practicing with peers, familiarizing oneself with the content, and watching instructional videos online, might help students overcome their lack of confidence in academic speaking (Ningrum & Listyani, 2022). It has also been discovered that integrating speaking simulations, real-world examples, constructive criticism, and a methodical approach in classroom settings helps students improve their communication skills and successfully lower their anxiety connected to public speaking (W & S, 2025). Furthermore, after finishing a public speaking course, many students have expressed feelings more secure and confident, demonstrating the benefits of organized speaking practice (Hidayah & Puspitasari, 2023).

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers conclude that the respondents have generally applied the coping mechanisms to improve public speaking skills presented by the researchers. Table 2 shows that the respondents always applied the coping mechanism indicators 1 to 6 with the median score of 4.00. Respondents sometimes used the following indicators, 7 to 11, which have a median score of 3.00. These suggest that those students have applied the coping mechanisms to improve public speaking skills presented by the researchers. Table 3 shows that the respondents agreed with statements 1 to 6, each receiving a median score of 4.00. Meanwhile, statements 7 to 9 received a median score of 3.00, indicating neutral responses. According to Achekzai and Adib (2024), encouraging students to speak English during class participation can be achieved by fostering their self-confidence, providing engaging assignments, cultivating supportive relationships, and creating a positive learning environment. Although speaking English in class causes little fear for most students, some individuals may still experience nervousness when speaking in front of large groups (Kella, 2021). To help learners face the prospect of speaking English with confidence, it is important to address the challenges related to speech production. As Axrorovna and Baxtiyorovna (2020) explain, this essay focuses on enhancing students' confidence in speaking English by examining the difficulties commonly encountered by English language learners. The respondents assured their self-confidence in public speaking which implied that grade 12 students in Mindanao State University-Sulu have confident in speaking English publicly.

Additionally, simple linear regression analysis revealed a significant result which means that applying coping mechanism will enhance their self-confidence in public speaking leads to .529 increase in self-confidence in public speaking.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study on coping mechanisms to enhance self-confidence and skills, the following recommendations are offered to support Grade 12 students at Mindanao State University-Sulu:

1. Students can enhance their self-confidence and skills in public speaking by practicing, using healthy coping strategies, establishing peer support groups, and utilizing technology and multimedia tools. These strategies can help lessen fear, provide a secure environment for practice, and foster a sense of comfort with public speaking.
2. Future researchers should conduct further studies based on the coping mechanisms to enhance self-confidence and skill in public speaking in different setting.
3. Teachers should use creative techniques to evaluate students' academic performance and encourage self-confidence and public speaking skills, while fostering a secure and motivating classroom environment.
4. Parents should teach their children to communicate with everyone. They should boost their children's confidence level in public speaking. Proper guidance from parents will help the students to enhance their self-confidence and skill in public speaking.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers affirm that this study was conducted in full compliance with ethical standards. Informed consent was duly obtained from all respondents prior to their participation, and they were clearly informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any point without any consequences. The anonymity and confidentiality of all participants were strictly maintained, and every effort was made to safeguard their well-being throughout the research process. The researchers declare that there were no conflicts of interest in the conduct of this study. Additionally, the interpretation of the findings was carried out with objectivity, without bias, and the results were used solely for academic and research purposes.

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REFERENCES

- Achekzai, P. Z. (2024). Exploring Strategies to Facilitate Student Participation in Speaking Classes. *Integrated Journal for Research in Arts and Humanities*, 4(4), 184–189. <https://doi.org/10.55544/ijrah.4.4.29>
- Ananda, N. & Hastini, H. (2023). A Study on Self-Confidence Impact of ELF Students' Speaking. *Journal of General Education and Humanities*, 2(3), 237–246. <https://doi.org/10.58421/gehu.v2i3.158>
- Aqso, D., Mulyadi, M., Rimbano, D., & Surajiyo, S. (2023). The Relationship between Self-Confidence and Public Speaking Ability of Students of the Faculty of Education Ahmad Dahlan University Yogyakarta. *Proceedings International Conference on Business Economics & Management*, 1, 161–172. <https://doi.org/10.47747/icbem.v1i1.1274>
- Axrorovna, K. U., & Baxtiyorovna, A. M. (2020). Being more confident in speaking English. *International Journal of Research*, 7(4), 9–12. <https://journals.pen2print.org/index.php/ijr/article/download/19799/19437>
- Dansieh, S. A., Owusu, E., & Seidu, G. A. (2021). Glossophobia: The fear of public speaking in ESL students in Ghana. *Language Teaching*, 1(1), 22. <https://doi.org/10.30560/lt.v1n1p22>
- Dias Lopes, L. F., Chaves, B. M., Fabrício, A., Porto, A., Machado de Almeida, D., Obregon, S. L., Pimentel Lima, M., Vieira da Silva, W., Camargo, M. E., da Veiga, C. P., de Moura, G. L., Costa Vieira da Silva, L. S., & Flores Costa, V. M. (2020). Analysis of Well-Being and Anxiety among University Students. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(11), 3874. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17113874>
- Hidayah, N., & Puspitasari, D. (2023). Students' learning experiences in public speaking: Challenges and strategies. *Tomorrow's Education Journal*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.58660/tej.v1i2.49>
- Inayah, R., & Lisdawati, I. (2021). Exploring Students' Difficulties in Speaking English and Their Attitude In Speaking English. *Acuity: Journal of English Language Pedagogy, Literature and Culture*, 2(1), 12-23. <https://doi.org/10.35974/acuity.v2i1.585>
- Kella, P. (2021). Factor of unwillingness to communicate English: Focusing on the anxiety in speaking. *ASELS 2021*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.51773/asels2021.v1i1.43>
- Nadiah, N. (2019). The students' self-confidence in public speaking. *Elite Journal*, 1(1), 1-12.
- Ningrum, N., & Listyani, L. (2022). Academic speaking students' efforts in minimizing their lack of self-confidence. *Prominent: Journal of English Studies*, 5(2). <https://doi.org/10.24176/pro.v5i2.7874>

- Permatasari, N. P. I. (2024). Interactive video project to boost university students' self-confidence in English public speaking. *Esteem Journal of English Education Study Programme*, 7(2), 689–697. <https://doi.org/10.31851/esteem.v7i2.16434>
- Pratiwi, A. E., Budiastuti, R. E., & Setiawan, A. (2024). Students Challenges in Learning Public Speaking. *Proceedings Series on Social Sciences & Humanities*, 18, 48–57. <https://doi.org/10.30595/pssh.v18i.1225>
- Putri, R., Rohbiah, T., & Asari, A. (2024). Implemented question and answer techniques to improve students' speaking ability. *Scope: Journal of English Language Teaching*, 8(2). <https://doi.org/10.30998/scope.v8i2.14964>
- Safitri, L., Jaya, A., & Khasanah, J. (2023). Applying the storytelling method to improve public speaking skill for English students. *FRASA: English Education and Literature Journal*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.47701/frasa.v4i1.2623>
- Salsabila, S., Putri, Z., & Muchsin, M. (2023). The correlation between students' self-confidence and speaking ability: A correlation study at SMAN 11 Banda Aceh. *Jurnal Edukasi El-Ibtida'i Sophia*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.32672/jeis.v2i1.6197>
- Sawchuk, C. N. (2024, December 20). Fear of public speaking: How can I overcome it? Mayo Clinic. Retrieved from <https://www.mayoclinic.org/diseases-conditions/specific-phobias/expert-answers/fear-of-public-speaking/faq-20058416>
- Shelton-Strong, S. J., & Mynard, J. (2018). Affective factors in self-access learning. *Relay Journal*, 1(2), 275–292. <https://doi.org/10.37237/relay/010204>
- W, A., & S, R. (2025). Strategy for building communication skill and self-confidence. *International Journal of Linguistics, Communication, and Broadcasting*, 2(4). <https://doi.org/10.46336/ijlcb.v2i4.161>
- Yaikhong, K., & Usaha, S. (2012). A measure of EFL public speaking class anxiety: Scale development and preliminary validation and reliability. *English Language Teaching*, 5(12), 23–35. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v5n12p23>
- Zhang, X., Ardasheva, Y., & Austin, B. W. (2020). Self-efficacy and english public speaking performance: A mixed method approach. *English for Specific Purposes*, 59, 1-16. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esp.2020.02.001>